

DETAILED GEOLOGICAL MAPPING AND 3D MODELLING FOR LUNAR RESOURCES EXPLORATION UNDER DATA CONSTRAINTS: AN APPROACH FOR RARE EARTH ELEMENTS CASE. M. J. Pereira Nunes Segundo¹ and A. Calzada Diaz¹, ¹European Space Resources Innovation Centre/Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology – ESRIC/LIST (mercio-john.pereira-nunes-segundo@list.lu).

Introduction: Off-Earth resources exploration faces important constraints due the lack of ground-truth data and scarce in-situ and, mainly resources-purpose, samples. In contrast to terrestrial mineral exploration workflows, we are forced to rely predominantly on orbital remote sensing datasets and contour the limited direct geochemical validation.

Geological Mapping plays a pivotal role in the exploration workflow. It not only shows where the resources are located, but all the context that they are inserted, while 3D modelling incorporate an important aspect of mineral deposits: depth.

In planetary settings, its necessary extract interpretations from the data, rely in assumptions, while gathering uncertainties from many sources. Nevertheless, this does not diminish its importance and geological mapping remains indispensable, providing the only systematic basis for preliminary resource assessment, decision-making, while address the data gaps.

This work presents efforts in compiling and interpreting different lunar data sets from previous missions, to perform the most detailed geological maps, using it as basis for 3D models and sample-assumption based resources estimative in REEs areas.

Methodology: Based on the Selene-Kaguya GRS data, which contains the most recent Th concentration results, were defined three main interest areas ^[1]: (1) Bossa Nova Target, (2) Lalande Target and (3) Apollo 14 Target. The first two areas were mapped using NAC Images, RGB composite images derived from M³ Chandrayaan-1 images on ENVI Classic v.5.7, Mineralogy/Elemental Abundance Maps derived from Selene-Kaguya Multiband Imager (MI) ^[2] and Christensen Feature ^[3] from LRO's Diviner.

To the present date, only Bossa Nova was modelled. It was performed using Seequent's Leapfrog Geo v.2024.1 using average thickness single values reported in previous studies for some units, while other part was subject to the authors' interpretation based in terrestrial examples.

Results: *Geological mapping:* Based in Th and REEs geochemical trend and key meteoritic sample descriptions (SaU 169 and Calalong Creek), in which evolved clasts are identified as the primary carriers of REEs, a first-order delimitation of small areas characterized by low Christensen Feature values were interpreted as a possible association with the occurrence of a relative more evolved lithologies.

These areas are spatially correlated with topographically controlled crests and ejecta deposits^[4].

Hyperspectral Analysis: The preliminary hyperspectral image analysis aimed at investigating absorption features potentially associated with Nd³⁺ was not conclusive. However, it may represent one of the first indications of a possible spectral signature attributable to this element on the lunar surface. Its basis relied on the combination of simple band depth spectral parameters at 730 nm and 870 nm, corresponding to the principal absorption windows associated with Nd³⁺ electronic transitions., suggesting a potential co-occurrence of Nd³⁺ within topographic crests, further reinforcing the preliminary assumptions regarding these zones as REE exploration targets.

This is congruent with preliminary observations from Lalande Crater, where the E crater wall presents the same absorption bands in a consistent location.

Modelling and Resources Estimate: The first 3D geological, numerical models (Figure 1) and resource estimate for REEs in lunar deposits is presented here. Although preliminary and requiring further refinement, the implicit model yields the following insights:

Both numerical models (1- using combined GRS data only and 2 - adding sample data) confirm that mare units exhibit relatively lower concentrations of thorium (Th) and, by extension, REEs, whereas highland regions consistently show higher Th content.

The Th-block model (Figure 1c-e), which simulates only the distribution of evolved lithologies to a depth of 50 meters, refines this understanding. According to this model, topographic crests tend to present higher Th concentrations, whereas ejecta-related zones show relatively lower grades.

Using the block volumes, and assuming that the REE content in apatite and merrillite from the lunar meteorite SaU 169 is representative of the "evolved facies" unit, the same mineral modal proportions and TREO (La, Ce, Nd, and Y in oxide form) concentrations reported for this meteorite were assigned to each kilogram of rock, considering a density of 3000 kg·m⁻³.

The conservative bulk-rock estimate of 2803 ppm TREO, when extrapolated to volume, corresponds to approximately 12,700 kt of REEs across a 10 m regolith layer and 40 m of "bedrock".

In this sense, Bossa Nova can have grades comparable with, and often exceeding, phosphorites deposits reported grades on Earth.

Figure 1. Numerical and Block Models for *Bossa Nova* Target. In (A) is show the Model 1, that combine data from Lunar Prospector (2 x 2 degrees) and Selene Kaguya GRS; (B) the Model 2, includes SaU 169 Th concentrations added manually. (C) Block Model for Th. (D-E) View in details of the blocks showing higher grades over the topographic crests.

Conclusions: This study demonstrates that, despite the intrinsic limitations of planetary datasets and the absence of systematic ground-truth validation, an integrated geological mapping and 3D modelling approach can provide a structured and defensible framework for preliminary Rare Earth Element (REEs) resource assessment on the Moon.

The compilation and reinterpretation of orbital geochemical, mineralogical, hyperspectral, and morphological datasets enabled the identification of spatial correlations between thorium (Th) enrichment, interpreted evolved lithologies, and topographically controlled crests within the Bossa Nova target area.

Although hyperspectral indications of Nd^{3+} remain subtle and require further validation, their spatial consistency with CF data and Th anomalous zones reinforces the exploration rationale.

The first-order 3D numerical and block models suggest that evolved highland-related units may host REE grades comparable to, and in some cases exceeding, terrestrial phosphorite deposits when evaluated under conservative assumptions.

While the resource estimates presented here are preliminary and model-dependent, they illustrate the potential of data-driven, assumption-explicit methodologies to reduce uncertainty and guide exploration prioritization in off-Earth environments. Ultimately, this work highlights geological mapping and 3D modelling as indispensable tools for bridging data gaps, structuring risk, and advancing the maturity of lunar REE exploration strategies.

References: [1] Pereira Nunes II, M. J. (2025). [Unpublished master's thesis]. European Space Resources Innovation Centre (ESRIC), GeoPlaNet Master Programme. [2] Greenhagen et al., 2010. *Science*, 329(5998), 1507–1509. [3] Lemelin et al., 2016, 47th LPSC, abs. #2994. [4] Pereira Nunes II, M. J. & Calzada Diaz, A. (2025), ELS 2025.

